

Light Scattering Behaviour of Thorium Phosphate Gel-forming System

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The changes in depolarization values and in intensity of transversely scattered light of thorium phosphate gels, prepared by diluting acid solutions of thorium phosphate, have been investigated. The results show that the particles grow in size owing to agglomeration. This study also reveals that the particles in the set gels are very nearly spherical in shape. The intensity values show a gradual change initially; thereafter it attains a steady value. The dissymmetry ratio $I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$ fails to provide true indication of probable shape of the particles in this system.

Thorium phosphate gels were first prepared by Prakash and Dhar (this *Journal*, 1929, 6, 587) by mixing thorium nitrate and potassium phosphate solutions in suitable concentrations. The gels obtained were either transparent or translucent. Mehta, Parmar and Prasad (*ibid.*, 1936, 13, 128) have shown that perfectly transparent gels of thorium phosphate could be obtained by using phosphoric acid, instead of potassium phosphate. They reported that perfectly transparent gels could also be obtained by suitably diluting a saturated solution of thorium phosphate in hydrochloric acid. The optical properties of these gels, prepared by directly mixing solutions of thorium nitrate and potassium phosphate, have been studied in details by Desai and Guruswami (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1943, 18A, 31) and by Prasad and Doss (*J. Col. Sci.*, 1949, 4, 349). The former have studied the effect of HCl and non-electrolytes on the rate of change of opacity of these gels, while the latter examined the changes in intensity of the depolarisation factors of transversely scattered light by these gel-forming mixtures during their setting.

In this investigation a study has been made of the changes in depolarisation factors and in intensity of the transversely scattered light during setting of thorium phosphate gels, prepared by the dilution method of Mehta *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Gelatinous precipitate of thorium phosphate was obtained by mixing adequate quantities of 10% solutions of potassium phosphate and thorium nitrate. The precipitate was washed free of impurities with hot distilled water, and dried at 110°. A saturated solution of thorium phosphate was then made in 2.96*N*-HCl. An equal volume of 2.96*N*-HCl was added to this solution; the resulting solution was filtered repeatedly through a sintered bed filter (A. G. 201 × 4). The strength of this stock solution was estimated as 6.740 g. ThO₂/litre.

A definite volume of the stock solution was taken in one test tube and in another test tube was taken a known volume of an electrolyte, diluted to such an extent that total volume of the solution after mixing was always 50 c.c. The content of one test tube was then poured into another and back again. The resulting mixture was shaken for about 30 seconds and transferred immediately to the optical cell for measurement of depolarisation and intensity of scattered light during the process of gelation. Measurements of depolarisation values ρ_u , ρ_v and ρ_h , and the intensity of transversely scattered light (I_{90°) were made at known intervals of time, after mixing, as described earlier (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 645; 1960, 37, 282). Electrolytes used were KNO₃ (1.0 *M*), K₂HPO₄ (0.05*M*), and thorium nitrate (0.0125*M*).

The results of these measurements for one particular system are recorded in Table I in which ρ_u , ρ_v , and ρ_h are expressed as percentages and the intensity values I_{90° are given in arbitrary units.

TABLE I

Thorium phosphate soln. = 1.0 c.c. Shunt = 4500 ohms. Time of setting = 12.5 mins.

Time.	ρ_u .	ρ_v .	ρ_h (calc.).	I_{90}° .	$I_{45}^\circ/I_{135}^\circ$.	Time.	ρ_u .	ρ_v .	ρ_h (calc.).	I_{90}° .	$I_{45}^\circ/I_{135}^\circ$.
1 min.	8.22	3.96	86.35	0.50	3.00	30 min.	3.27	0.85	34.73	1.25	3.28
3	5.99	2.65	75.76	0.60	3.16	40	3.27	0.85	34.73	1.50	3.42
5	4.71	1.85	62.76	0.80	3.20	50	3.27	0.85	34.73	1.75	3.47
7	4.71	1.85	62.76	0.90	3.25	60	3.27	0.85	34.73	1.75	3.47
10	4.71	1.85	62.76	1.00	3.28	80	3.27	0.85	34.73	1.75	3.47
15	4.33	1.51	52.31	1.00	3.28	100	3.27	0.85	34.73	1.75	3.47
20	3.61	1.01	38.31	1.25	3.28	120	3.27	0.85	34.73	1.75	3.47

DISCUSSION

The data recorded in Table I indicate a decrease in the ρ_v values from about 4.14 to 0.62% during setting time in the gel-forming systems containing increasing amounts of thorium phosphate as well as different amounts of electrolytes. Similar observations have been made by Ramiah (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 5A, 138) in the case of silicic acid gels. These observations show that in the gel-forming system under investigation, the gel structure is being built up of particles, which are initially anisotropic in nature. As the setting of gel progresses with lapses of time, anisotropy of the particles becomes less and less until finally the particles in the set gels are very nearly isotropic in shape and/or structure.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

It is seen further that the particles in the set gels are very nearly spherical in different systems containing increasing amounts of thorium phosphate and different electrolytes.

The ρ_h values were obtained from the observed values of ρ_u and ρ_v using Krishnan's relation.

$$\rho_h = \frac{1 + 1/\rho_v}{1 + 1/\rho_u}$$

(*ibid.*, 1935, 1A, 717, 782). It is observed that the values of ρ_h show a decrease during setting of the gels, indicating commencement of agglomeration of the particles resulting in the increase

of their size. The final values of ρ_b show that the size of the particles in the set gels is comparatively large with respect to the wave lengths of the incident light used.

The changes in the intensity of transversely scattered light with time are shown in Table I and in Fig. 1. It is observed that the intensity of the transversely scattered light goes on increasing with time and at a certain stage the intensity reaches a maximum; thereafter it remains steady. These observations reveal that in the initial stage the process of agglomeration takes place which results in the increase in size, incidently in the number of the particles as well. At a certain stage, when the intensity reaches a maximum, the process of agglomeration is complete. This happens when the gel is set; after setting there is no change in size and number of the particles, as indicated by the horizontal part of the curve.

The effect of adding electrolytes on the intensity values is clearly seen from the curves (Figs. 2-4). With increase in concentrations of KNO_3 and K_2HPO_4 , the increase in the value of intensity is observed while thorium nitrate shows the reverse effect. These observations show that electrolytes (KNO_3 , K_2HPO_4) help the process of agglomeration, thus causing increase in particle size while thorium nitrate facilitates peptisation.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

Density and Anisotropy Scattering

The density scattering (I_D) and the anisotropy scattering (I_A) have been separated from the total intensity (I_{90°) of the transversely scattered light. The values of I_D and I_A have been calculated from the relation (cf. Zimm *et al.*, *Polymer Bull.*, 1945, 1, 90):

$$I_D = I \times \frac{6 - 7\rho}{6 + 6\rho};$$

$$I_A = I - I_D = I \times \frac{13\rho}{6 + 6\rho}$$

and are shown in Table II.

The values of the density scattering (I_D) thus appear to increase with time while the anisotropy scattering (I_A) goes on decreasing with time during setting of the gels. The increase in the I_D values shows a gradual increase in the particular size owing to agglomeration, while the decrease in I_A values indicates that the particles, which are anisotropic in the beginning, become less and less anisotropic in shape and/or structure, ultimately attaining spherical shape when the gel is set.

TABLE II

Thorium phosphate soln. = 1.0 c.c. Time of setting = 8.0 mins. 1.0M-KNO₃ = 3.0 c.c.

Time.	ρ_v	$\rho = \frac{2\rho_v}{1+\rho_v}$	$\frac{6-7\rho}{6+6\rho}$	I_{90}°	I_D	I_A
5 min.	2.80	0.0545	0.8882	0.80	0.7106	0.0894
7	2.37	0.0463	0.9040	0.90	0.8136	0.0864
10	1.85	0.0363	0.9158	1.00	0.9158	0.0842
15	1.85	0.0363	0.9158	1.00	0.9158	0.0842
20	1.73	0.0341	0.9270	1.10	1.0210	0.0790
30	1.30	0.0257	0.9456	1.20	1.1340	0.0660
40	1.30	0.0257	0.9456	1.30	1.2290	0.0710
50	0.93	0.0184	0.9610	1.50	1.4420	0.0580
60	0.69	0.0137	0.9709	2.00	1.9420	0.0580
80	0.69	0.0137	0.9709	2.00	1.9420	0.0580
100	0.69	0.0137	0.9709	2.00	1.9420	0.0580
120	0.69	0.0137	0.9709	2.00	1.9420	0.0580

Dissymmetry : Ratio $I_{45}^\circ/I_{135}^\circ$

The values of the ratio $I_{45}^\circ/I_{135}^\circ$ are shown in Table I. It will be seen that the values lie between 3.0 and 5.5. It appears from these observations that the particles are initially disc-shaped. The data, obtained from the depolarisation factor ρ_v , indicate, however, the possibility of the particles attaining more or less spherical shape in the set gels. The dissymmetry : ratio $I_{45}^\circ/I_{135}^\circ$ does not give true indication of the probable shape of the particles in these gel-forming systems.

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